

A cross-sectional investigation on the hearing findings of leprosy patients in Maluku, rural Indonesia

Semiramis Zizlavsky ^{1,*}, Natasha Supartono ¹, Rodrigo Limmon ², Sri Linuwih Soesetyo Wardhani Menaldi ³, Yunia Irawati ⁴, Luh Karunia Wahyuni ⁵

¹ Department of Otorhinolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery (ORL-HNS), Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National General Hospital, Faculty of Medicine Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia.

² Department of Otorhinolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery, Faculty of Medicine, Pattimura University, Maluku, Indonesia.

³ Department of Dermatovenereology, Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National General Hospital, Faculty of Medicine Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia.

⁴ Department of Ophthalmology, Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National General Hospital, Faculty of Medicine Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia.

⁵ Department of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine, Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National General Hospital, Faculty of Medicine Universitas, Jakarta, Indonesia.

*. **Corresponding author:** Semiramis Zizlavsky, Department of Otorhinolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery (ORL-HNS), Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National General Hospital, Faculty of Medicine Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia. Phone: +62 8129229027. Email: semiramiszizlavsky@gmail.com.

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Abstract

Background: Leprosy, a neglected tropical illness caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, has a substantial socioeconomic and psychological impact in Indonesia, which ranks third in global prevalence. Despite well-documented dermatological and neurological effects, auditory problems of leprosy, such as hearing loss, remain largely unknown. The purpose of this study is to look at the spectrum of hearing impairment in leprosy patients in Maluku, Indonesia's highest leprosy burden area, and to identify critical variables that may lead to hearing loss in these individuals.

Methods: A cross-sectional study of 98 leprosy patients was carried out in Maluku, Indonesia. Audiological evaluations included otoacoustic emissions to measure cochlear function and pure tone audiometry to test hearing sensitivity. Bivariate analyses were used to compare group characteristics, with statistical significance defined at $p < 0.05$. The study followed STROBE principles for transparent reporting.

Results: Among 98 patients (196 ears) evaluated, 26% had hearing loss, primarily sensorineural (71.7%) and of mild severity (76.5%). The median age of participants was 32 years, and older patients (>40 years) had considerably higher hearing thresholds ($p < 0.001$). Leprosy reactions were associated with higher hearing thresholds at 4000 Hz ($p = 0.015$), and corticosteroid therapy was linked to better hearing outcomes in individuals with reactions.

Conclusion: This study reveals a significant prevalence of sensorineural hearing loss among leprosy patients in Maluku, which is strongly associated with age and leprosy responses. Corticosteroid medication appears to have a protective effect on hearing function, highlighting the importance of regular auditory examinations and focused therapies to enhance patient outcomes in this population.

Keywords: Leprosy, Hearing loss, Sensorineural hearing loss, Otoacoustic emission, Audiometry, Indonesia

Introduction

Leprosy, a neglected tropical illness caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, is a major public health concern, despite a decreased global prevalence of 0.22 cases per 10,000 people in 2019 (1). This condition causes severe morbidity and imposes a socioeconomic and psychological burden on afflicted patients and communities (1). Indonesia is third in prevalence (19,938 cases), after India (79,898) and Brazil (31,827) (2). Although Indonesia reached national eradication status in 2000, with a prevalence rate of 4.4 cases per 100,000 people, new cases are still emerging, particularly in Eastern Indonesia, such as Maluku (3). Maluku has one of the highest leprosy prevalence rates in Indonesia, with 2.08 cases per 10,000 people, much higher than the national rate of 0.74 cases per 10,000 people in 2019 (4). Furthermore, Maluku had the second-highest incidence of new leprosy cases in 2022 (4), underscoring the critical need for targeted actions to combat leprosy in this region, as well as the ability to shed light on Indonesia's overall leprosy burden.

Leprosy is most known for its negative effects on skin health and structure, the peripheral nervous system, the eyes, and the mucous membranes. It can cause a variety of clinical symptoms, including sensory loss, peripheral neuropathy, and persistent rhinitis (5). Although the dermatological and neurological effects of leprosy are well established, auditory consequences linked with the disease, particularly hearing loss, have received significantly less attention, exposing a huge research vacuum that requires additional examination (6,7). Previous research has found a consistent prevalence of hearing loss in leprosy patients, ranging from 25% to 75%, with the majority experiencing mild sensorineural hearing loss (8,9). This prevalence is higher than in the general population, where roughly 20% of the global population suffers from hearing loss, highlighting the need to explore the particular reasons contributing to this disproportionately high prevalence in leprosy patients (10).

In Indonesia, where leprosy is still a public health concern, hearing loss from various causes affects around 4.6% of the population, with a deafness prevalence of 2.6%. This places Indonesia fourth in Southeast Asia for hearing loss prevalence, after only Sri Lanka, Myanmar, and India (11). However, specific statistics on the prevalence of hearing loss related with leprosy in Indonesia are currently unavailable. The relationship between leprosy and hearing impairment may be modified by local risk factors such as infections and the use of ototoxic drugs, as well as demographic issues associated with aging (8). While hearing loss has been linked to leprosy, there is currently little research on the audiological

characteristics of leprosy patients in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), including Indonesia. As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the spectrum of hearing loss in leprosy patients in Maluku, Indonesia's highest leprosy burden area, and to discover the major variables that contribute to hearing loss in these individuals.

Methods

Following approval from the local ethical committee (KET-698/UN2.F1/ETIK/PPM.00.02/2022), the *Identifikasi Tanda-tanda Kelainan Mata, Kulit, & Ekstremitas pada Kusta* (KATAMATAKU) team, which included medical experts from various disciplines such as ophthalmologists, dermatologists, psychiatrists, and otorhinolaryngologists from the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia, conducted this cross-sectional study. Between March 10 and 11, 2023, we collaborated with local health officers to recruit patients with a past leprosy diagnosis in Maluku. All participants provided written informed consent. The inclusion criteria were as follows: 1) patients who had previously received multidrug therapy (MDT) for leprosy, and 2) patients who could cooperate and follow instructions. Patients were excluded if they had: 1) psychiatric, neurological, or intellectual problems; 2) presbycusis; 3) a current or previous history of a perforated tympanic membrane; or 4) an acute or chronic ear infection. The minimum sample size was determined using an online sample size calculator (Raosoft, Inc., WA, US; 2004). With a population of 388 leprosy patients in Maluku, a disease prevalence of 50%, and a 10% margin of error, this study required at least 96 participants (192 ears) (12,13). This study follows the STROBE cross-sectional reporting guidelines (14).

Three otorhinolaryngologists conducted interviews in a quiet but non-soundproof room (with a mean ambient broadband noise level of less than 20 dB sound pressure level) to collect demographic information, clinical characteristics of leprosy, including the presence of leprosy reaction, the duration and type of MDT, and any treatment modifications. In addition, all patients had physical ear examinations and audiological assessments, which included otoacoustic emission (OAE; GSI Corti, Grason-Stadler Inc., MN, US; 2012) testing at frequencies ranging from 1500 Hz to 12,000 Hz and pure tone audiometry (MA 42, MAICO Diagnostics, MN, US; 2017).

Table 1. Patient characteristics, overall and stratified by hearing function

Characteristics	Total (n=98)	Hearing loss		P-value
		Yes (n=35)	No (n=63)	
Age	32.0 (21.8-46.0)	44.0 (36.0-57.0)	25.0 (20.0-35.0)	<0.001
<40 years	63 (64.3)	11 (31.4)	52 (82.5)	
≥ 40 years	35 (35.7)	24 (68.6)	11 (17.5)	
Sex				0.211
Male	62 (63.3)	25 (71.4)	37 (58.7)	
Female	36 (36.7)	10 (28.6)	26 (41.3)	
Leprosy type (n=82)				0.429 ^a
Multibacillary	74 (90.2)	23 (85.2)	51 (92.7)	
Paucibacillary	8 (9.8)	4 (14.8)	4 (7.3)	
Leprosy-specific MDT (n=82)				0.429 ^a
Dapsone, rifampicin, clofazimine	74 (90.2)	23 (85.2)	51 (92.7)	
Dapsone, rifampicin	8 (9.8)	4 (14.8)	4 (7.3)	
Duration of treatment (months; n=96)	12.0 (6.0-36.0)	12.0 (6.0-39.0)	12.0 (6.0-36.0)	0.749
Leprosy reaction (n=86)	30 (34.9)	8 (28.6)	22 (37.9)	0.393
Type 1	6 (20.0)	3 (37.5)	3 (13.6)	0.300
Type 2	24 (80.0)	5 (62.5)	19 (86.4)	
Steroid use	37 (40.7)	10 (33.3)	27 (44.3)	0.318

Unless otherwise stratified, data are presented in frequencies (proportions) and medians (interquartile ranges), and analyzed using Chi-square statistics. ^aP-value derived from Fisher's exact test. MDT: multidrug therapy.

Table 2. Findings of hearing examinations among the recruited subjects

Hearing characteristic	Total (n=196)	Right ear (n=98)	Left ear (n=98)
Hearing loss	51 (26.0)	25 (25.5)	26 (26.5)
Type			
Conductive	12 (26.1)	6 (25.0)	6 (27.3)
Sensorineural	37 (71.7)	18 (75.0)	15 (68.2)
Mixed	1 (2.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (4.5)
Severity			
Mild	39 (76.5)	22 (84.6)	17 (68.0)
Moderate	9 (17.6)	4 (15.4)	5 (20.0)
Moderate-severe	2 (3.9)	0 (0.0)	2 (8.0)
Severe	1 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (4.0)
Profound	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Hearing threshold (dB)	17.5 (13.8-25.3)	17.5 (13.8-25.0)	17.5 (14.4-26.1)
500 Hz (n=193)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)
1000 Hz (n=194)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)
2000 Hz (n=194)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)
4000 Hz (n=194)	10.0 (5.0-25.0)	10.0 (5.0-25.0)	10.0 (5.0-25.0)
Abnormal acoustic emission test (n=194)			
1500 Hz	67 (34.5)	33 (34.0)	34 (35.1)
2000 Hz	61 (31.4)	31 (32.0)	30 (30.9)
3000 Hz	79 (40.7)	40 (41.2)	39 (40.2)
4000 Hz	80 (41.2)	41 (42.3)	39 (40.2)
5000 Hz	95 (49.0)	51 (52.6)	44 (45.4)
6000 Hz	115 (59.3)	54 (55.7)	61 (62.9)
7000 Hz	133 (68.6)	63 (64.9)	70 (72.2)
8000 Hz	118 (60.8)	55 (56.7)	63 (64.9)
9000 Hz	119 (61.3)	58 (59.8)	61 (62.9)
10000 Hz	125 (64.4)	59 (60.8)	66 (68.0)
11000 Hz	134 (69.1)	55 (67.0)	69 (71.1)
12000 Hz	151 (77.8)	74 (76.3)	77 (79.4)

Data are presented in frequencies (proportions) and medians (interquartile ranges).

Table 3. Comparison of hearing characteristics of the recruited patients by age

Hearing characteristics	Age (years)		P-value
	<40	≥40	
Hearing loss	25 (25.5)	26 (26.5)	<0.001 ^a
Type			>0.999 ^b
Conductive	4 (26.7)	8 (25.8)	
Sensorineural	11 (73.3)	22 (71.0)	
Mixed	0 (0.0)	1 (3.2)	
Severity			0.118 ^b
Mild	14 (87.5)	25 (71.4)	
Moderate	1 (6.3)	8 (22.9)	
Moderate-severe	0 (0.0)	2 (5.7)	
Severe	1 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	
Hearing threshold (dB)	12.1 (9.9-15.0)	24.4 (18.8-35.0)	<0.001 ^c
500 Hz (n=193)	20.0 (10.1-25.0)	30.0 (25.0-40.0)	<0.001 ^c
1000 Hz (n=194)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	25.0 (20.0-35.0)	<0.001 ^c
2000 Hz (n=194)	10.0 (9.3-10.0)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	<0.001 ^c
4000 Hz (n=194)	5.0 (12.7-10.0)	25.0 (10.0-36.3)	<0.001 ^c
Abnormal acoustic emission test (n=194)			
1500 Hz	37 (29.8)	30 (42.9)	0.067 ^a
2000 Hz	28 (22.6)	33 (47.1)	<0.001 ^a
3000 Hz	44 (35.5)	35 (50.0)	0.049 ^a
4000 Hz	39 (31.5)	41 (58.6)	<0.001 ^a
5000 Hz	50 (40.3)	45 (64.3)	0.001 ^a
6000 Hz	61 (49.2)	54 (77.1)	<0.001 ^a
7000 Hz	74 (59.7)	59 (84.3)	<0.001 ^a
8000 Hz	64 (51.6)	54 (45.8)	<0.001 ^a
9000 Hz	66 (53.2)	53 (75.7)	0.002 ^a
10000 Hz	68 (54.8)	57 (81.4)	<0.001 ^a
11000 Hz	75 (60.5)	59 (84.3)	0.001 ^a
12000 Hz	89 (71.8)	62 (88.6)	0.007 ^a

^aP-values derived from Chi-square statistics. ^bP-values derived from Monte-Carlo exact method with a sample size of 51 hearing-impaired patients. ^cP-values derived from Mann-Whitney U test

Table 4. Comparison of hearing characteristics by leprosy type and reaction among the recruited patients

Hearing characteristics	Leprosy type; n (%)		P	Leprosy reaction; n (%)		P
	Multibacillary (n=148, 90.2%)	Paucibacillary (n=16, 9.8%)		Present (n=38, 33.3%)	Absent (n=76, 66.7%)	
Hearing loss	34 (23.0)	4 (25.0)	0.766 ^a	12 (20.0)	29 (25.9)	0.387 ^c
Hearing threshold (dB)	17.4 (12.8-23.8)	21.3 (14.7-26.3)	0.408 ^b	16.3 (12.5-21.3)	18.8 (13.8-26.3)	0.088 ^b
500 Hz (n=193)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)	25.0 (18.8-35.0)	0.800 ^b	25.0 (15.0-30.0)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)	0.179 ^b
1000 Hz (n=194)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	25.0 (15.0-30.0)	0.468 ^b	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	20.0 (15.0-26.3)	0.486 ^b
2000 Hz (n=194)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	0.413 ^b	12.5 (10.0-20.0)	15.0 (10.0-20.0)	0.435 ^b
4000 Hz (n=194)	10.0 (5.0-25.0)	17.5 (8.8-27.5)	0.473 ^b	10.0 (5.0-18.8)	10.0 (5.0-26.3)	0.031^b
Abnormal otoacoustic emission test (n=172)						
1500 Hz	54 (37.0)	3 (18.8)	0.147 ^c	21 (36.2)	41 (36.6)	0.959 ^c
2000 Hz	45 (30.8)	6 (37.5)	0.585 ^c	18 (31.0)	32 (28.6)	0.738 ^c
3000 Hz	62 (42.5)	6 (37.5)	0.702 ^c	21 (36.2)	46 (41.1)	0.538 ^c
4000 Hz	59 (40.4)	7 (43.8)	0.796 ^c	22 (37.9)	47 (42.0)	0.612 ^c
5000 Hz	71 (48.6)	8 (50.0)	0.917 ^c	24 (41.4)	60 (53.6)	0.132 ^c
6000 Hz	85 (58.2)	10 (62.5)	0.741 ^c	31 (53.4)	68 (60.7)	0.362 ^c
7000 Hz	100 (68.5)	11 (68.8)	0.983 ^c	40 (69.0)	75 (67.0)	0.791 ^c
8000 Hz	87 (59.6)	10 (62.5)	0.822 ^c	35 (60.3)	63 (56.3)	0.608 ^c
9000 Hz	87 (59.6)	11 (68.8)	0.477 ^c	37 (63.8)	65 (58.0)	0.468 ^c
10000 Hz	94 (64.4)	11 (68.8)	0.728 ^c	39 (67.2)	68 (60.7)	0.403 ^c
11000 Hz	103 (70.5)	10 (62.5)	0.569 ^a	40 (69.0)	76 (67.9)	0.883 ^c
12000 Hz	116 (79.5)	13 (81.3)	>0.999 ^a	45 (77.6)	89 (79.5)	0.776 ^c

Data are presented in frequencies (proportions) and medians (interquartile ranges). ^aP-values derived from Fisher's exact test. ^bP-values derived from Mann-Whitney U test. ^cP-values derived from Chi-square statistics.

Table 5. Comparison of hearing characteristics by leprosy type and reaction among patients aged <40 years old

Hearing characteristics	Leprosy type; n (%)			Leprosy reaction; n (%)		
	Multibacillary (n=100, 90.9%)	Paucibacillary (n=10, 9.1%)	P	Present (n=38, 33.3%)	Absent (n=76, 66.7%)	P
Hearing loss	13 (13.0)	1 (10.0)	>0.999 ^a	1 (2.6)	11 (14.5)	0.059 ^a
Hearing threshold (dB)	15.0 (9.1-23.1)	15.0 (12.3-19.7)	0.962 ^b	25.0 (15.0-25.0)	25.0 (20.0-30.0)	0.106 ^b
500 Hz (n=193)	22.5 (16.3-38.8)	25.0 (20.0-25.0)	0.689 ^b	20.0 (15.0-20.0)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	0.125 ^b
1000 Hz (n=194)	17.5 (7.5-28.8)	20.0 (15.0-25.0)	0.790 ^b	10.0 (10.0-15.0)	10.0 (10.0-15.0)	0.302 ^b
2000 Hz (n=194)	12.5 (6.3-18.8)	10.0 (10.0-15.0)	0.990 ^b	5.0 (5.0-10.0)	10.0 (5.0-15.0)	0.200 ^b
4000 Hz (n=194)	12.5 (1.3-20.0)	10.0 (5.0-15.0)	0.763 ^b	15.0 (11.3-17.3)	15.0 (12.4-21.3)	0.015^b
Abnormal otoacoustic emission test (n=112)						
1500 Hz	34 (34.7)	1 (10.0)	0.162 ^a	11 (30.6)	23 (30.3)	0.975 ^c
2000 Hz	22 (22.4)	4 (40.0)	0.249 ^a	8 (22.2)	13 (17.1)	0.517 ^c
3000 Hz	36 (36.7)	4 (40.0)	>0.999 ^a	11 (30.6)	25 (32.9)	0.804 ^c
4000 Hz	31 (31.6)	3 (30.0)	>0.999 ^a	8 (22.2)	24 (31.6)	0.306 ^c
5000 Hz	41 (41.8)	3 (30.0)	0.523 ^a	9 (25.0)	33 (43.4)	0.060 ^c
6000 Hz	49 (50.0)	5 (50.0)	>0.999 ^a	14 (38.9)	39 (51.3)	0.219 ^c
7000 Hz	61 (62.2)	5 (50.0)	0.506 ^a	22 (61.1)	43 (56.6)	0.650 ^c
8000 Hz	51 (52.0)	6 (60.0)	0.746 ^a	19 (52.8)	35 (46.1)	0.506 ^c
9000 Hz	53 (54.1)	6 (60.0)	>0.999 ^a	18 (50.0)	39 (51.3)	0.896 ^c
10000 Hz	56 (57.1)	6 (60.0)	>0.999 ^a	19 (52.8)	40 (52.6)	0.988 ^c
11000 Hz	63 (64.3)	5 (50.0)	0.494 ^a	20 (55.6)	47 (61.8)	0.526 ^c
12000 Hz	74 (75.5)	7 (70.0)	0.708 ^a	25 (69.4)	56 (73.7)	0.640 ^c

^aP-values derived from Fisher’s exact test. ^bP-values derived from Mann-Whitney U test. ^cP-values derived from Chi-square statistics.

Table 6. Association between leprosy reaction and steroid administration and hearing threshold at 4000 Hz (n=164)

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Group 1	15.0 (8.8-26.3)			
Group 2	>0.999	10.0 (5.0-23.8)		0.064
Group 3	>0.999	>0.999	10.0 (5.0-21.3)	
Group 4	0.054	>0.999	>0.999	10.0 (5.0-25.0)

P-values were derived from Kruskal-Wallis H test followed by Mann-Whitney U test for pairwise comparison, and were adjusted by Bonferroni’s correction for multiple comparisons.

Group 1: No leprosy reaction without steroid use (n=82)

Group 2: No leprosy reaction with steroid use (n=24)

Group 3: Leprosy reaction without steroid use (n=10)

Group 4: Leprosy reaction with steroid use (n=48)

Patient age was dichotomized using a cutoff of 40 years, based on earlier research indicating that hearing function declines as early as age 40 (15) and the observed data distribution, which indicated a natural threshold at this age. Hearing loss was classified as conductive, sensorineural, or mixed, with severity levels of normal (hearing threshold <25 dB), mild (25-40 dB), moderate (41-54 dB), moderate-to-severe (55-69 dB), severe (70-89 dB), and profound (≥ 90 dB).

The obtained data were maintained in Microsoft Excel 2010 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA) and analyzed in SPSS 25.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). Continuous data were displayed as medians and interquartile ranges (IQR), whereas dichotomous data were represented by frequencies and proportions. Pearson's Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests were used to compare groups for dichotomous variables, and the Mann-Whitney U test was used for continuous data. When Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests were not practicable, we used the Monte-Carlo exact test (16). P-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using Bonferroni's correction, and the statistical significance level was set at 5%.

Results

103 patients were screened for inclusion in the current study. Five individuals were excluded: three had a history of presbycusis, one was unwilling to comply and follow instructions, and one had a perforated tympanic membrane. Thus, this investigation included 98 leprosy patients (196 ears). The median age of the patients was 32 years (IQR 21.8-46.0 years), with the majority being male (62, 63.3%) and suffering with multibacillary leprosy (74, 90.2%). Patients with hearing loss were significantly older than those without (median age 44.0 years [IQR 36.0-57.0] vs. 25.0 years [20.0-35.0], $p < 0.001$). There were no significant differences seen between sexes ($p = 0.211$), leprosy type (multibacillary vs. paucibacillary, $p = 0.429$), treatment length ($p = 0.749$), leprosy reactions ($p = 0.393$), or steroid use ($p = 0.318$) (Table 1). Of the 196 ears evaluated, 51 (26.0%) had hearing loss, with a roughly similar distribution between the right and left ears (25 [25.5%] vs. 26 [26.5%]). Sensorineural hearing loss was detected in 37 ears (71.7%), conductive hearing loss in 12 (26.1%), and mixed hearing loss in one patient (2.2%). Of the 51 ears with hearing loss, 39 had mild hearing loss (76.5%), 9 had moderate hearing loss (17.6%), 2 had moderate-to-severe hearing loss (3.9%), and 1 had severe hearing loss (2.0%). No patient experienced substantial hearing loss (0%). Overall, the median hearing threshold for all patients was 17.5 dB [IQR: 13.8-25.3 dB], with 17.5 dB [13.8-25.0 dB] in the right ears and 17.5 dB [14.4-26.1 dB] in the left ears.

The median hearing thresholds were 25.0 dB [IQR: 20.0-30.0 dB] at 500 Hz, 20.0 dB [IQR: 15.0-25.0 dB] at 1000 Hz, 15.0 dB [IQR: 10.0-20.0 dB] at 2000 Hz, and 10.0 dB [IQR: 5.0-25.0 dB] at 4000 Hz. Abnormal OAE observations became more common at higher frequencies, with 67 ears (34.5%) at 1500 Hz and 151 ears (77.8%) at 12,000 Hz (Table 2). Age was the most significant confounder in this investigation, with older and younger patients having significantly different hearing thresholds and OAE findings across all frequencies (Table 3).

A subgroup analysis by leprosy type found no significant variations in hearing loss prevalence, hearing threshold at 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 Hz, or abnormal OAE tests (Table 4). Patients who did not have a leprosy reaction had a slightly higher median hearing threshold at 4000 Hz than those who did (10.0 dB [IQR 10.0- 15.0 dB] versus 10.0 dB [IQR 10.0- 15.0 dB], $p = 0.302$), even after controlling for age-related confounding factors (Table 5). Furthermore, individuals with leprosy reactions who received corticosteroids had a lower median hearing threshold at 4000 Hz than patients who did not have a leprosy reaction (10.0 dB [IQR 5.0-25.0 dB] vs 15.0 dB [IQR 5.8-26.3 dB] (Table 6).

Discussion

Hearing loss was detected in around 25% of leprosy patients in this investigation, with mild sensorineural hearing loss being the most common feature among all individuals. Despite this, the pathophysiological mechanisms that cause hearing loss in leprosy patients are not well understood. Previous study has revealed that leprosy bacilli can infect Schwann cells, causing neuronal ischemia that eventually leads to irreparable nerve damage (8,17). This damage is particularly severe in people with leprosy responses (18).

The prevalence of hearing loss in leprosy patients varies per study. Gopinath and colleagues discovered that 22% (22/100) of Indian leprosy patients had auditory nerve involvement (18). Similarly, Koyuncu and colleagues discovered sensorineural hearing loss of cochlear origin in 22% (8/39) of leprosy patients and vestibular dysfunction in 11% (4/39) of patients, but none of the age- and sex-matched non-leprosy patients showed hearing or vestibular impairment (19). Nayak and colleagues discovered that around 33% of Indian leprosy patients (10/33) exhibited high-frequency sensorineural hearing loss (6). Previous research has repeatedly demonstrated an elevated risk of hearing loss in leprosy patients (8,9), albeit

these values are not significantly different from the global prevalence of hearing loss (~20%) (10). Several other causes may contribute to leprosy patients' hearing loss. In this study, we discovered that age is the most important predictor of hearing loss, even in the absence of a history of presbycusis. This could be due to decreased cochlear function and auditory nerve degeneration. Furthermore, older patients are more likely to use ototoxic medicines and are more susceptible to noise pollution from traditional manufacturing, industries, and military forces. These findings corroborate our hypothesis that age contributes significantly to hearing impairment in leprosy patients, implying that the effects of aging may combine synergistically with the auditory diseases associated with leprosy (15). This emphasizes the significance of targeted auditory examinations in older leprosy patients, who may face increased risks of hearing deterioration due to both aging and the underlying disease process.

We found no significant relationship with leprosy type or reaction and overall hearing impairment. However, we discovered that leprosy reaction was linked with hearing threshold at 4000 Hz, even after controlling for the potential confounding effect of age. Hearing impairment has been described as a rare consequence of type 2 leprosy due to severe brain inflammation caused by a significant increase in bacterial load. Surprisingly, the hearing threshold of patients with leprosy reaction receiving corticosteroids was significantly lower than that of patients without leprosy reaction, implying that corticosteroids may have a protective effect on hearing function in leprosy patients. This is consistent with our understanding that corticosteroids effectively treat acute inflammation generated by the host's immunological response to *Mycobacterium leprae*. Corticosteroids are commonly started at 40 mg daily and discontinued over six months, while there are several regimens available without clear evidence from randomized controlled trials. Short courses of prednisolone, such as 12 weeks, are beneficial for neuritis, while low-dose preventive prednisolone during the first months of MDT minimizes new responses and nerve damage. As a result, the improvement in auditory thresholds among leprosy patients using corticosteroids could be attributed to their involvement in lowering inflammation and nerve damage. Nonetheless, these data do not support the use of corticosteroids to treat leprosy-related hearing loss. Further research investigating the long-term risk-benefit of corticosteroid treatment in hearing-impaired leprosy patients is needed (20).

There is insufficient information on the audiological characteristics of Indonesian leprosy patients. Despite global leprosy eradication efforts, Indonesia remains a

low- and middle-income country (21). The country remains one of the most impacted regions, providing considerable issues for the healthcare system (22). This emphasizes the crucial importance of ongoing leprosy control measures, early detection, and appropriate treatment to manage the illness and its sequelae. Regular auditory examinations for leprosy patients, particularly those aged 40 and up, may aid in the early diagnosis of hearing damage. When combined with timely and successful leprosy treatment, this may reduce the burden of leprosy-related hearing loss and enhance patients' quality of life. In rural locations where audiograms are not available (23), simple tests such as whispered voice or tuning fork examinations, in addition to a full history and physical examination of the ear, might be used (24). Leprosy patients with suspected hearing loss should be directed to specialized healthcare facilities for diagnosis and treatment. Furthermore, with the rapid growth of technology, digital diagnostic tools and tele-audiology services can be used to improve accessibility to hearing healthcare (23,25).

The study has significant limitations. First, because this is a cross-sectional study, the observed connections may not indicate causal relationships between factors. Second, even though stratified analysis was used, our results may not fully account for the confounding effects of age. Third, the lack of a control group reduces the capacity to quantify the risk of hearing loss related with leprosy. Finally, the limited sample size limits the generalizability of the findings. More large-scale, high-quality research are required to overcome these limitations and close the remaining evidence gaps in these populations. Furthermore, investigating other potential variables may help us better understand hearing loss in leprosy patients.

Conclusion

In conclusion, sensorineural hearing loss is very common among leprosy patients in Indonesia. Even in the absence of presbycusis, age is still the most major contributor to hearing loss in these people. While no significant relationships were discovered between leprosy type, response, and total hearing impairment, corticosteroids may alter the disease course of hearing loss in leprosy patients. We advocate regular auditory examinations for older leprosy patients to aid in the early diagnosis of hearing loss and enhance patient outcomes.

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